

51st National Metallurgists' Day
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and

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ABSTRACTS

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Department of Metallurgical Engineering

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The main objective was to re-engineer the process chemistry in the submerged arc furnaces to include high-MnO slag (silica: 25-30%) and quartz (silica: 98%) into the raw material blend and thus substitute high-silica manganese ores (silica: 20-35%). In-house R&D trials were conducted to ascertain the dissolution patterns of silica from quartz and slag, their reducibility etc. under various operating parameters. With the inputs from R&D trials, plant trials were done. Separate campaigns for slag and quartz trials were done for 20 and 15 days respectively. Higher alumina content in slag and low dissolution of silica from quartz were the problems encountered during slag and quartz trials respectively. Henceforth trials with quartz and slag together were done and process variables like electrode penetration, tapping consumption, flux input etc. were changed to get the desired results.

The figures from FY'13 on a year-on-year basis show the following trends-(a) reduction in consumption of high-silica ore and medium-grade ore by 50% and 19% respectively, (b) reduction in specific power consumption by 7% and increase in plant throughput by 0.5%.

Usage of quartz and/or slag in ferromanganese industry will help manufacturers become self-reliant, save precious manganese ores and will make their business model more sustainable.

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X.P.17 ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK APPROACH TO KROLL'S MAGNESIO-THERMIC REDUCTION PROCESS FOR ZIRCONIUM SPONGE PRODUCTION

P101

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Artificial neural network approach is a fascinating tool, inspired by the biological nervous system, that can be used to simulate a wide variety of complex scientific and engineering problems. A powerful artificial neural network function is determined largely by the interconnections between artificial neurons, similar to those occurring in their natural counterparts of biological systems. A certain amount of experimental results are required to train a well-defined neural network. Once the network has learned to map the reaction sequences, new data from the similar domain can be predicted without doing actual reduction process.

In India, Kroll's magnesio-thermic reduction process is used for production of reduced mass followed by vacuum distillation in order to get nuclear grade zirconium sponge. In reduction operation, sublimed ZrCl₄ vapors are reacting with molten magnesium to form zirconium sponge. The efficiency of reduction operation depends upon many parameters like initial weight of the ZrCl₄ taken for reaction, pressure profile, slope of the pressure trend, temperature profile, energy consumption, time required for the

completion of the reaction, and Number of bleeds, etc., All of the above mentioned process parameters are well linked to control the percentage recovery. An attempt is made by approaching the neural scheme for optimizing the efficiency of the reduction reaction by considering the weighted average of the each unit to provide an additive contribution to the input of the unit with which it is connected. The total input to unit k is simply the weighted sum of the separate outputs from each of the concerned units plus a bias or offset term θ_k Which is explained in Fig.1 Within the neural systems it is useful to distinguish three types of units for finding the percentage recovery as follows: (i) input units which receive data from outside the neural network, (ii) hidden unit whose input and output signals remain within the neural network and (iii) output unit which send data out of the neural network.

$$s_k(t) = \sum_j w_{jk}(t) y_j(t) + \theta_k(t)$$

Fig.1 The basic components of artificial neural network

where, s_k – the new level of activation based on the effective input; w_{jk} – the weight of the signal of unit j has on unit k; y_j – State of activation equivalent to the unit j for every unit, which equivalent to the output of the unit; θ_k External input to unit k for each unit.

X.P.18 COMPARISON OF GRAIN REFINEMENT IN ALUMINUM ALLOY BY INOCULATION AND DYNAMIC NUCLEATION

P102

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Inoculation is a common practice in industry for achieving grain refinement in Aluminum Alloys. Grain refinement offers unique advantage in property of the Casting. Another technique Dynamic Nucleation with forced convection by mechanical stirring and passing of inert gas prove to be better choice for obtaining the desired characteristics which is generally not used in the commercial scale. The particle size of the secondary nuclei, particle density of the Aluminum alloy was studied using the combined effect of Inoculation and Dynamic Nucleation methods. The effect of particle density of the secondary nuclei on the microstructure was also considered. The study was aimed at finding whether grain refinement can be effectively achieved by applying forced convection to obtain better grain refinement than the conventional methods of inoculation and increasing the convection level in an